

IceDetectNet: a rotated object detection algorithm for classifying components of aggregated ice crystals with a multi-label classification scheme

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Abstract. The shape of ice crystals affects their radiative properties, growth rate, fall speed, and collision efficiency; thus, it plays a significant role in cloud optical properties and precipitation formation. Ambient conditions, like temperature and humidity, determine the basic habit of ice crystals, while microphysical processes, such as riming and aggregation, further shape them, resulting in a diverse set of ice crystal shapes and effective densities. Current classification algorithms face two major challenges: (1) ice crystals are often classified as a whole (at the image scale), necessitating identification of the dominant component of aggregated ice crystals, and (2) single-label classifications lead to information loss because of the compromise between basic habit and microphysical process information. To address these limitations, we present a two-pronged solution here: (1) a rotated object detection algorithm (IceDetectNet) that classifies each component of an aggregated ice crystal individually and (2) a multi-label classification scheme that considers both basic habits and physical processes simultaneously. IceDetectNet was trained and tested on two independent datasets obtained by a holographic imager during the NASCENT campaign in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard, in November 2019 and April 2020. The algorithm correctly classified 92 % of the ice crystals as either aggregate or non-aggregate and achieved an overall accuracy of 86 % for basic habits and 82 % for microphysical process classification. At the component scale, IceDetectNet demonstrated high detection and classification accuracy across all sizes, indicating its ability to effectively classify individual components of aggregated ice crystals. Furthermore,

the algorithm demonstrated a good generalization ability by classifying ice crystals from an independent generalization dataset with overall accuracies above 70 %. IceDetectNet can provide a deeper understanding of ice crystal shapes, leading to better estimates of ice crystal mass, fall velocity, and radiative properties; therefore, it has the potential to improve precipitation forecasts and climate projections.

1 Introduction

The shape of ice crystals within clouds impacts the Earth's radiation budget (Ehrlich et al., 2008; Sun and Shine, 1994; Matus and L'Ecuyer, 2017; Flanner et al., 2007; Järvinen et al., 2018). As ice crystals interact with solar and terrestrial radiation, they scatter, absorb, and emit radiation, thereby influencing the radiative properties of the atmosphere (Flanner et al., 2007; Järvinen et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2015). Furthermore, the shape of ice crystals has a substantial effect on global precipitation, influencing both the spatial distribution and precipitation rate (Sterzinger and Igel, 2021; Woods et al., 2007; Jensen et al., 2017). The growth mechanisms of ice crystals play a crucial role in precipitation formation (Wegener, 1911; Findeisen, 1938; Lohmann et al., 2016; Kalina and Puxbaum, 1994; Mosimann et al., 1993). The efficiency of these processes is largely determined by the ice crystal shape, further highlighting its importance (Heymsfield, 1972;

Khvorostyanov and Curry, 2002; Bailey and Hallett, 2004; Mitchell, 1996; Mitchell et al., 1990; Wang and Ji, 2000).

The initial shape of an ice crystal, also known as its basic habit (e.g., column or plate), is governed by the ambient meteorological conditions, such as the temperature and supersaturation, that it experiences during its initial diffusional growth phase (Libbrecht, 2016; Bailey and Hallett, 2004). The change in the ambient environment, such as in a convective system, leads to a complex basic habit, such as columns on capped columns (CPCs; observed by Pasquier et al., 2023). They are further shaped by microphysical processes, including riming (i.e., supercooled cloud droplets collide and freeze on the ice crystal) and aggregation (i.e., individual ice crystals collide and stick together). This leads to a wide range of ice crystal shapes, sizes, and densities, introducing considerable challenges with respect to the systematic classification of ice crystals.

Early ice crystal classification techniques used simple features like edge complexity (Cunningham, 1978), circular deficiency (Rahman et al., 1981), the surface area and perimeter (Durooure et al., 1994), and the complexity (combined of several geometric features, such as the particle area and area ratio) (Schmitt and Heymsfield, 2014) to classify the shape of ice crystals, but they cannot distinguish between composite ice crystals, such as irregular crystals, aggregates, or bullet rosettes. More advanced techniques, like ice crystal classification with principal component analysis (Lindqvist et al., 2012) and logistic regression (Praz et al., 2017), have been developed and have achieved 80%–90% accuracy, but they still require manual feature extraction (e.g., aspect ratio). Furthermore, these algorithms have demonstrated limitations with respect to their ability to perform effectively on different datasets, as their classification performance is strongly influenced by the characteristics of the training dataset (Bishop and Nasrabadi, 2016; Goodfellow et al., 2016), which is defined as the generalization ability of the models. This dependency requires significant adjustments to the optimal thresholds when these algorithms are applied to new, unseen datasets.

The emergence of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) as part of deep learning algorithms has introduced significant improvements to the classification of ice crystal habits, with their capability for automated feature extraction (Li et al., 2021; Albawi et al., 2017; Touloupas et al., 2020). Although CNNs exhibit a remarkable capacity to recognize key aspects of images, they struggle when faced with complex ice crystals such as CPCs or aggregates consisting of different basic habits (Zhang, 2021). Furthermore, CNNs that are based on single-label classification schemes face the challenge of information loss when composite ice crystals are classified (Zhang, 2021; Xiao et al., 2019). For example, an aggregated column can only be labeled either as “aggregate” or column, which results in information loss with respect to either the basic habit or the microphysical process. According to the study by Korolev et al. (1999), in Arctic clouds, pristine ice

habits (ice crystals that have not undergone any microphysical processes) account for only 3% of the particles observed, which would result in losing a substantial fraction (97%) of ice information regarding either basic habits or microphysical processes when implementing a single-label classification scheme if the ice habits are still recognizable. Moreover, in stratiform clouds, Korolev et al. (2000) found that 84% of the ice crystals are irregular ice, which is everything except needles and dendrite. These irregular ice crystals would be either aged or aggregated by our definition (see Sect. 2 and Appendix B). To tackle this problem, Zhang et al. (2022) first proposed that the ice shape label should contain two types of information: the basic habits and the microphysical processes that the ice has experienced. Thus, they recommend that a multi-label should be assigned to one ice crystal. Jaffeux et al. (2022) combined data from the Precipitation Imaging Probe and 2DS-Stereo Probe to train CNNs to classify ice crystals according to their basic habit and the occurrence of riming and aggregation. Although their study considered potential microphysical processes for each ice crystal category manually after the CNN classification, the specific microphysical processes associated with individual components of an aggregated ice crystal remained unknown.

To summarize, there are two key limitations of current ice crystal classification algorithms:

1. Algorithms often classify the images of an ice crystal as a whole, necessitating the identification of the dominant component of an aggregated ice crystal; thus, they are not able to account for the presence of multiple basic habits in an aggregated ice crystal.
2. Single-label classification algorithms require a compromise between basic habit and microphysical process information, leading to information loss.

To address these issues, we propose a novel approach that consists of a rotated object detection algorithm (called IceDetectNet) along with a multi-label classification scheme. IceDetectNet can classify the ice crystals down to the scale of aggregated ice crystal components with both basic habit and microphysical process information, thereby eliminating the need to identify a dominant aggregated component. The multi-label classification scheme simultaneously accounts for both the basic habits and microphysical processes of an ice crystal, reducing information loss. However, like all supervised learning methods, our approach is limited to the ice categories present in the training dataset, limiting its applicability until the model is fine-tuned on a new dataset. The data used to train and test IceDetectNet are described in Sect. 2. The structure of IceDetectNet is presented in Sect. 3. The performance of our proposed algorithm is evaluated in Sect. 4. Finally, Sect. 5 and Sect. 6 present the relevant discussion and conclusions of this study, respectively.

2 Data description

The data used in this study were collected in Arctic mixed-phase clouds during the NASCENT campaign (Pasquier et al., 2022a) conducted in Ny-Ålesund, Norway. Ice crystal images were captured by the HOLIMO holographic imager mounted on the HoloBalloon tethered balloon system (Ramelli et al., 2020). The measured ice particle sizes ranged from 50 μm to 2.4 mm. First, the cloud particles were classified as cloud liquid droplets and ice crystals using a convolutional neural network (CNN) approach, as described in Touloupas et al. (2020). This preliminary classification served as the basis for the subsequent detailed classification of the ice crystals.

Following this initial categorization, each ice crystal was classified into one of seven basic habits: column, plate, lollipop (Pasquier et al., 2022a), CPC, irregular, frozen droplets, and small. Our seven basic habit categories were determined by their presence and distinct shape features observed in our dataset collected in the aforementioned Arctic mixed-phase clouds in Ny-Ålesund. These basic habit classes are based on the categories used in Pasquier et al. (2022a), as we used the same dataset. Additionally, up to two microphysical process attributes (i.e., aggregate and aged) were assigned to each ice crystal. Table 1 describes the seven basic habits and four microphysical process categories (i.e., pristine, aged, aggregate, and aged and aggregate). Thus, the final habit classification of an ice crystal is a combination of the basic habit and microphysical processes (i.e., the final classification = basic habit + microphysical processes). Not all combinations of basic habits and microphysical processes are feasible, resulting in a total of 19 ice classes (examples are shown in Fig. B1) rather than the theoretically possible 28 (7×4) categories. For instance, the small class refers ice crystals that are too small to determine their habit, making it impossible to derive their microphysical processing. Furthermore, all ice crystals in the lollipop, CPC, and irregular classes are defined as aged ice instead of pristine ice (as they are not newly produced ice), although they are still basic habit categories. For a more detailed discussion of the categorization criteria, we refer to Appendix B. However, due to data limitations, our dataset does not capture every possible basic ice habit, such as needles and rosettes, although the existence of these ice habits is well acknowledged (Kikuchi et al., 2013). This limitation is acknowledged and further discussed in Sect. 5, where we look at potential extensions to IceDetectNet. As new data containing additional ice habits become available, IceDetectNet can be updated, as it is designed to incorporate these new habits through fine-tuning, ensuring the continued evolution of the model.

The dataset collected on 11 November 2019 (Pasquier et al., 2022b), hereafter the training dataset, was used to train IceDetectNet. During the training, it was divided into a training subset (comprising 80 % of the data) and a validation subset (made up of the remaining 20 %), using a cross-validation

method (see the detailed introduction in Sect. 3.8.1). This validation subset serves a similar purpose to the traditional test sets used in other studies (Jaffeux et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2019; Touloupas et al., 2020), providing an initial evaluation of the model's performance under known conditions. On the other hand, the generalization dataset was collected on a different date, 1 April 2020 (Pasquier et al., 2022b), and is not used during training; rather, it is employed to evaluate the generalization abilities of IceDetectNet.

Table 2 offers a summary of both the training and generalization datasets. The training dataset consists of 18 864 ice particles, where the column and CPC classes were dominant, accounting for 47.5 % of the ice crystals in the training data. Non-pristine ice, which is ice that is not freshly formed, accounts for 70.5 % of the ice crystals in the training data. Additionally, 18.8 % of the non-pristine ice crystals have undergone two microphysical processes, and aggregated ice makes up 12 % of the ice crystals in the training dataset.

In contrast, the generalization dataset has a significant fraction of irregular (47.3 %) and small (23.4 %) ice crystals (Fig. B1). Unlike the training dataset, the generalization dataset does not include any instances of the lollipop or CPC classes and, consequently, the corresponding compound categories “lollipop–aggregate” or “CPC–aggregate” do not exist. Moreover, the generalization dataset only contains three occurrences of the frozen droplet class, with small numbers for “frozen droplet–aged” (8) and “frozen droplet–aged–aggregate” (12), while “frozen droplet–aggregate” is not present. The proportion of non-pristine ice increases from 70.5 % in the training dataset to 93.9 % in the generalization dataset. The fraction of aggregate ice increases from 11.9 % in the training dataset to 37.7 % in the generalization dataset.

The difference between the training and generalization datasets is an example of the natural variability in field observations. In our case, the two datasets were collected during different seasons, resulting in variations in the environmental conditions. The training dataset was collected in the temperature range from -8 to -3 °C (mostly in the column regime), whereas the generalization dataset was collected between -23 and -15 °C (mostly in the plate regime) (Pasquier et al., 2022b). These differences allow us to assess the generalization ability of IceDetectNet and to examine its performance under diverse environmental conditions.

3 Methodology

In this section, we first provide an overview of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which serve as the foundation for the object detection algorithm in IceDetectNet. We start by explaining the overall structure of CNNs (Sect. 3.1), followed by an introduction to the rotated object detection algorithm developed in this study and implemented into IceDetectNet (Sect. 3.2). Subsequently, we discuss the data preparation (Sect. 3.4) and training process (Sect. 3.7), outlining

Table 1. Description of the ice crystal categories, including seven basic habits and four microphysical process categories.

Property	Class	Description
Basic habits	Column	Columnar ice crystal
	Plate	Plate-like ice crystal
	Frozen droplet	Frozen cloud or drizzle droplets characterized by nonspherical shapes or distortions
	Small ^a	Ice crystals that seem small during visual assessment by the hand labeler (usually smaller than 75 μm)
	Columns on capped columns (CPC) ^b	Ice crystals that contain both columnar and plate-like features, often resembling a “H”; formed when growing in both the column and plate temperature regimes (Pasquier et al., 2023)
	Lollipop ^b	Formed when a supercooled droplet collides with columns and freezes upon impact (Keppas et al., 2017)
	Irregular ^b	Irregular-shaped ice crystal with no clearly defined ice habit
Microphysical processes	Pristine	Ice crystals with an easily identifiable shape that have not undergone any microphysical processes
	Aged	Ice crystals that have undergone microphysical processes such as riming or sublimation
	Aggregate	Ice particles that are composed of two or more ice crystals stuck together
	Aged and aggregate	Ice crystals that have undergone both aging and aggregation

^a Ice crystals are categorized as pristine. ^b Ice crystals are categorized as aged.

the essential steps for training the model. Lastly, the evaluation metrics are introduced that are used to assess the performance of IceDetectNet on the training dataset and its ability to generalize to the unseen generalization dataset (Sect. 3.8).

3.1 Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)

CNNs are a class of neural networks widely recognized for their exceptional performance in image classification tasks (Gu et al., 2018; Albawi et al., 2017; Rawat and Wang, 2017; Touloupas et al., 2020). CNNs consist of a specific architecture designed to extract meaningful features from images. The key components of a typical CNN include convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers (Fig. 1). These layers work together to enable effective image analysis. The convolutional layer scans the input image with a small filter or kernel, extracting low-level features such as edges and color. The pooling layer reduces the spatial size of the convolved feature (feature map shown in Fig. 1) and aims to decrease computational complexity. The fully connected layer, which is usually the final layer of a CNN, performs the classification using the flattened or pooled output from the preceding layers.

In practice, CNN structures can be much more complex than the basic CNN described above. He et al. (2016) proposed a deep residual learning approach that stores input information and propagates it directly from the first layer to the last. This approach has been successfully used in subse-

quent object detection algorithms that utilize the ResNet-50 structure (He et al., 2016). Due to this success, IceDetectNet (described in Sect. 3.5) is trained using the preexisting parameters of ResNet-50, which was trained on the ImageNet dataset consisting of approximately 1.3 million images labeled into 1000 categories, with the exception of the last layer due to the different number of categories in ice classification (Deng et al., 2009; He et al., 2016). This helps to speed up the training process and achieve better performance.

3.2 Rotated object detection algorithm

Building on the foundations of CNNs, object detection algorithms serve as an extension to detect and classify objects within images. While CNNs typically classify the image as a whole, object detection algorithms localize and classify specific objects within these images, providing both their location (through the bounding box) and class labels (Zhao et al., 2019). The rectangular box that tightly encloses the object of interest is called a bounding box (as shown in Fig. 2). Rotated object detection algorithms additionally predict the angle of rotation of the bounding box (Zou et al., 2023). In this study, we introduce such a rotated object detection algorithm for ice crystal classification as part of IceDetectNet. This algorithm classifies multiple components of aggregated ice crystals individually and predicts the center, the dimensions, and the rotation angle of bounding boxes enclosing the ice crystal components. This ensures that the ice components

Table 2. Overview of the number of ice crystals in each class for both the training and generalization datasets, along with illustrative examples for each class. The green circles with a plus symbol indicate that the corresponding ice class is part of the aggregate/non-pristine category in the dataset, while the orange circles with a minus symbol indicate the opposite. Please note that the examples shown are intended for visual reference only and may not be representative of the entire dataset.

Class	Train	Generalization	Aggregate	Non-Pristine	Example
Column	5442	329	−	−	
Plate	126	556	−	−	
Frozen droplets	201	3	−	+	
Small	1618	3393	−	+	
Columns on capped-columns	3509	0	−	+	
Lollipop	419	0	−	+	
Irregular	1106	3613	−	+	
Column-aged	3603	729	−	+	
Plate-aged	90	393	−	+	
Frozen droplets-aged	490	8	−	+	
Column-aggregate	17	44	+	+	
Column-aged-aggregate	794	1346	+	+	
Plate-aggregate	10	114	+	+	
Plate-aged-aggregate	90	711	+	+	
Frozen droplets-aggregate	65	0	+	+	
Frozen droplets-aged-aggregate	220	12	+	+	
Irregular-aged-aggregate	620	3239	+	+	
Capped column-aged-aggregate	409	0	+	+	
Lollipop-aged-aggregate	30	0	+	+	
Overall	18864	14490			

are captured within the smallest feasible rectangle, which offers a more accurate recognition of the object by minimizing the inclusion of background pixels (Ding et al., 2019). Here, we use the S2ANet network structure (Han et al., 2021) as the base structure of the rotated object detection algorithm within IceDetectNet.

3.3 Hand-labeling of bounding boxes and ice categories

Accurate hand labeling is essential for training IceDetectNet, as for all supervised learning methods. In contrast to conventional classification algorithms, rotated object detection models such as IceDetectNet require a two-step hand-labeling process: (1) locate the ice components within the images by drawing bounding boxes and (2) assign the appropriate category labels to each component based on our multi-label classification scheme.

Figure 1. General structure of a CNN with an example of ice crystal classification. The input ice crystal is classified into one of the ice classes based on computed probabilities, with the highest probability determining the assigned class. In this example, the input ice crystal is classified as “column-aged-aggregate” with a 70 % probability.

Structure of IceDetectNet:

Figure 2. Structure of the IceDetectNet algorithm, consisting of predicting potential bounding boxes (step 2), removing duplicate predicted bounding boxes (step 3), cropping the remaining bounding box for classification (step 4), and predicting the ice crystal categories of each bounding box (step 5). The yellow and orange dashed lines indicate bounding boxes predicted by the algorithm and their corresponding labels and confidence intervals (step 5), whereas the solid lines show the hand-labeled bounding boxes (step 3). The individual steps are described in the main text.

In the present study, both the training and generalization datasets were initially hand-labeled at the image scale using our multi-label ice classification scheme (Sect. 2). For the image-scale hand-labeling, the basic habit of the largest ice component is considered the basic habit of the image. Regarding microphysical processes, any image containing an

ice component with signs of aging was labeled “aged”. Additionally, images consisting of multiple ice components were categorized as “aggregated”. The image-scale hand-labeling served as the basis for the component-scale hand-labeling.

For the hand-labeling of non-aggregated ice crystals (identified using the hand label at the image scale), we applied an

automated method for drawing bounding boxes. The method uses the color contrast between the typically black ice pixels and the typically gray background to identify the location of the ice component regions. Then, we calculated the minimum bounding rectangle of the ice regions automatically as the bounding box of these non-aggregated ice crystals. The non-aggregated ice crystals were assigned the same ice category labels as the corresponding labels at the image scale.

For aggregated ice crystals, the hand-labeling of the bounding boxes (i.e., drawing) was done manually using the platform provided by AngoAI (2022), as illustrated in Appendix A and Fig. A1. Bounding boxes representing the minimum enclosing rectangle of each ice component were manually drawn. Furthermore, every bounding box was visually classified in an ice category following the multi-label classification scheme introduced in Sect. 2. In total, we manually labeled 2255 aggregated ice crystals and 16 609 non-aggregated ice crystal components. Note that the component-scale hand-labeling was only done for the training dataset due to the large effort involved with the hand-labeling of bounding boxes and ice categories. The generalization dataset was only hand-labeled at the image scale.

3.4 Image preprocessing

Before the image is fed into IceDetectNet, the initial image is enlarged by 15 % (with respect to both length and width), to ensure full bounding box coverage and maintain the aspect ratio (see input in Fig. 2), by adding black pixels (pixel values = 1) around the borders. This augmentation ensures that the entire bounding box is located within the image, even when parts of the bounding box extend beyond the original image frame. To ensure consistency across the network for training and testing, all images are then uniformly resized to 512 px × 512 px by employing bilinear interpolation after the enlargement.

The input images are normalized to meet the pretrained ResNet-50 model's input specifications. For example, the pretrained ResNet-50 model requires an RGB image as input, which consists of three dimensions by default. Given that our images only have one dimension, we replicate the single dimension three times to emulate the three-dimensional structure of RGB images and to produce pseudo-RGB images.

3.5 Inference process of IceDetectNet

The structure of the IceDetectNet algorithm is shown in Fig. 2. The input for IceDetectNet (step 1 in Fig. 2) comprises the processed images undergoing the preprocessing steps described in Sect. 3.4. The algorithm uses the ResNet-50 backbone network (He et al., 2016) to extract image features at a per-pixel scale. After feature extraction, IceDetectNet predicts potential bounding boxes for individual ice components (step 2 in Fig. 2). These predicted bounding boxes contain the location, size, and rotation angle of the respective ice com-

ponents. Multiple bounding boxes might be predicted for the same ice component, or some predicted bounding boxes may be too large to tightly capture an ice component, while others could be too small, missing some parts of an ice component (step 2 in Fig. 2). Prior to classification, duplicate bounding boxes are removed (step 3 in Fig. 2) by a feature alignment module (Sect. 3.6). The remaining predicted bounding boxes enclosing the individual ice components are the input for the classification module (step 4 in Fig. 2), which outputs a predicted ice label with a confidence level (step 5 in Fig. 2). After classification, a post-processing step is performed to further remove duplicate bounding boxes (step 6 in Fig. 2) by comparing all predicted bounding boxes instead of hand-labeled bounding boxes using the intersection over union (IoU) threshold and the confidence level of classification. The IoU quantifies the overlap between two predicted bounding boxes and is calculated as follows:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{area of overlap}}{\text{area of union}}. \quad (1)$$

If the IoU between two predicted bounding boxes exceeds a threshold, the bounding box with the lower confidence level is discarded. This threshold was set to 50 % in the present study to minimize the number of aggregated ice crystals misclassified as non-aggregated and vice versa. Previous studies suggested that an IoU threshold within the range of 50 % to 75 % leads to the best performance (Zhang et al., 2019).

3.6 Training process of IceDetectNet

The training phase of IceDetectNet is a crucial and complex process, as it requires a careful balance between reducing detection errors (step 2 in Fig. 2) and classification errors (step 5 in Fig. 2), all via a process of loss minimization. The feature alignment module (step 3 in Fig. 2) is trained to reduce the difference between the predicted and hand-labeled bounding boxes. If the IoU between a predicted and a hand-labeled bounding box is above 50 %, the prediction is considered correct (Zhang et al., 2019). On the contrary, an IoU below 50 % indicates an incorrect prediction, resulting in a loss that the training process then aims to minimize. To reduce the loss, a method called backpropagation is employed. Backpropagation adjusts the model's parameters to reduce errors and refines the feature extraction to improve the accuracy of the bounding box prediction in step 2. The primary objective of the feature alignment module is to fine-tune the orientation and position of bounding boxes, especially those with an IoU below 50 %. The images within the refined bounding boxes are then processed by the classification module. Incorrectly predicted labels contribute to the model's loss in classification, which is further minimized using backpropagation as well, leading to improved classification in step 5. Steps 6 and 7 belong to post-processing and are not subject to training.

3.7 Training details

The training details of IceDetectNet and the hyperparameters used during training are described here. To prevent the model from memorizing the training data (a problem known as “overfitting”) and to lower the generalization errors when it is applied to new unseen data, we introduced transformations to our training images. More specifically, we applied a technique called data augmentation which performs random flips of the images in the horizontal, vertical, and diagonal directions with a 25 % probability. During the inference, no data augmentation was applied to prevent any distortion in the final output.

The training was executed on a computational system equipped with four RTX 2080 GPUs. A batch size of 64 was chosen to optimize computational efficiency and training stability.

The learning rate underwent a structured adaptation during the training process as follows:

1. Initially, the learning rate was set to 0 and linearly increased to 0.0025 over the initial 500 steps. Here, a “step” is defined as a single iteration in the training process, in which one batch of data is processed to update IceDetectNet’s parameters.
2. After the first 500 steps, the learning rate was kept constant at 0.0025.
3. A reduction by a factor of 10 was applied at specific epochs; the learning rate was set to 0.00025 from the 64th to the 88th epochs and further reduced to 0.000025 after the 88th epoch. This decremental strategy aimed at refining model parameters with progressively smaller updates as the training advanced.

To ensure model robustness and prevent overfitting, we employed the early-stopping technique (Jabbar and Khan, 2015). Checkpoints were integrated to retain the best-performing model based on the validation dataset.

3.8 Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of IceDetectNet, we used a cross-validation approach (Sect. 3.8.1) and a range of evaluation metrics (Sect. 3.8.2): overall accuracy, precision, recall, and the confusion matrix, as highlighted in the following sections.

3.8.1 Cross-validation

IceDetectNet was validated by applying a 5-fold cross-validation approach, which is a method that minimizes the variance in performance estimation while also maximizing the use of available data for training (Browne, 2000). Here, we randomly partitioned the dataset into five equally sized subsamples or “folds”. Four of the five subsamples were used

for training the model, while the remaining subsample was retained as the validation data for testing the model. This process was then repeated five times (the folds), with each of the five subsamples used exactly once for validation. Each fold was designed to include images from every class, thus ensuring that the model was trained and evaluated on a diverse set of ice crystals from all categories. This helped to prevent bias in the evaluation of the model’s performance due to an unrepresentative selection of training and test data (Arlot and Celisse, 2010). The five outcomes from the folds were then averaged to produce a single estimation of IceDetectNet’s performance.

In future applications, if the performance of the five individual models is similar (performance is evaluated in Sect. 4), a single model could be selected for use, simplifying the process. Alternatively, the ensemble of five models can be used to make the final predictions, increasing reliability. For example, if three models predict one ice component as a column but two predict it as a plate, the component is predicted as a column. The advantage of this method over repeated random subsampling is that all ice crystals are used for both training and validation and each ice crystal is used for validation exactly once. This method, although computationally expensive, provides a robust evaluation of IceDetectNet’s performance and its ability to generalize to new, unseen data (Arlot and Celisse, 2010).

3.8.2 Evaluation metrics

To assess the performance of IceDetectNet, we employ several metrics that evaluate the model performance with regard to different aspects, including the overall accuracy, precision, recall, confusion matrix, and F1 score. The overall accuracy is defined as the ratio of the number of correct predictions to the total number of particles (Goodfellow et al., 2016). An overall accuracy of 100 % means that, for example, all ice particles were correctly predicted, whereas an overall accuracy of 0 % indicates that all particles were mispredicted. While overall accuracy provides a quick and straightforward metric to interpret the model performance, it can be misleading when dealing with imbalanced datasets where classes are not equally represented. In such cases, the model may perform well with respect to predicting the dominant classes but struggle to predict rare classes. Precision and recall both measure the accuracy of a deep learning classification model with respect to predicting a single category from two perspectives. Precision is calculated as the ratio of the number of correct predictions of a specific class to the total number of predictions (Goodfellow et al., 2016), while recall is defined by the ratio of the number of correct predictions of a specific class to the total number of this class (Goodfellow et al., 2016). A high precision score indicates effective identification of a specific class, while a high recall score indicates that the model excels in identifying instances of a particular class and is less likely to miss relevant instances that

belong to the class. All of these metrics can be combined and visualized in a so-called confusion matrix (Goodfellow et al., 2016). In a confusion matrix, the diagonal, from the top left to the bottom right, corresponds to correct predictions made by the model, whereas the elements outside of this diagonal represent misclassifications. The bottom-right cell of the matrix displays the total number of ice crystals and the overall accuracy. The bottom row provides the actual counts per class and their respective per-class precision. Similarly, the rightmost column presents the predicted counts per class and the associated per-class recall. The F1 score is a harmonized metric that combines precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of a model's performance, particularly in situations where the balance between precision and recall is critical (Goodfellow et al., 2016). This score reaches its best value at 1 (indicating perfect precision and recall) and its worst value at 0. In the context of IceDetectNet, a high F1 score would indicate not only that the model accurately identifies ice particles (high precision) but also that it successfully detects the majority of actual ice particles (high recall), making it a robust metric for evaluating model performance across different classes, especially in the presence of imbalanced datasets.

4 Results

4.1 Evaluation of model performance

The evaluation of IceDetectNet differs from traditional deep learning classification algorithms because both detection (Sect. 4.1.1) and classification (Sect. 4.1.2) steps need to be evaluated. As described in Sect. 3.8.1, we trained five models using a 5-fold cross-validation approach. Four folds were used for training, and the remaining fold was used for validation. A small portion of the images for which no bounding boxes were predicted (validation fold in training dataset: 11 of 3755) were labeled as “none” and excluded from the following analysis.

4.1.1 Performance of aggregate detection

The detection performance of IceDetectNet was examined by first evaluating the ability of the algorithm to distinguish between aggregate and non-aggregate ice. Images with a single bounding box were defined as non-aggregate ice, whereas images with multiple bounding boxes were defined as aggregate ice. The aggregate/non-aggregate detection was evaluated by comparing the number of predicted bounding boxes with the number of hand-labeled bounding boxes for the training dataset (Fig. 3a). Hand-labeled and predicted bounding boxes are in good agreement, with an overall accuracy of 92 %, reflecting the ability of IceDetectNet to correctly classify images as aggregated or non-aggregated ice.

To understand the source of the 8 % of misdetected aggregate and non-aggregate ice, we analyzed the number of

overdetected and underdetected bounding boxes. Here, we consider it over-detection when the algorithm predicts multiple bounding boxes for an ice crystal that is hand-labeled as non-aggregate (i.e., one bounding box) and under-detection when the algorithm predicts one bounding box for an ice crystal that is hand-labeled as aggregate (i.e., multiple bounding boxes). In absolute numbers, there were 266 instances of over-detection and 63 instances of under-detection (Fig. 3b). In relative terms, 40 % of the predicted aggregates were hand-labeled as non-aggregates (over-detection), resulting in a recall of 60 % for actual non-aggregates. Conversely, only 2 % of the predicted non-aggregates were hand-labeled as aggregates (under-detection), indicating a high recall of 98 % for actual aggregates (Fig. 3c). This shows that, while it tends to overestimate the presence of aggregates, the model is highly effective at identifying actual aggregates. Considering that only 12 % of the training dataset was aggregate ice (as detailed in Sect. 2), a few mispredictions of non-aggregate ice as aggregate can significantly increase the over-detection. For example, if 2 % (66) of the non-aggregate ice crystals were misclassified as aggregate, this would lead to a 14.6 % over-detection. Until this point, we have evaluated how well the predicted categories match the actual categories. As a complement, we now turn our attention to precision, examining the accuracy of the predictions in terms of correctly identified categories. The precision is 88.7 % for aggregate (i.e., 88.7 % of the predicted aggregates were hand-labeled as aggregates) and 77.1 % for non-aggregate, consistently showing the model's tendency to overpredict the numbers of bounding boxes.

To address the issue of the over-detection or under-detection of bounding boxes, it is possible to adjust the IoU threshold in the post-processing (as introduced in Sect. 3.2). In the present study, an IoU threshold of 50 % was applied to remove duplicate bounding boxes (see Fig. 2), but the IoU threshold can be changed based on the relative composition of the ice classes in the dataset. Generally, when an over-detection problem was identified, a higher IoU threshold could be implemented to reduce the number of detected bounding boxes, and the opposite adjustment could be made if under-detection was observed. Thus, the IoU threshold can be used as a tuning parameter to reduce/increase the number of bounding boxes kept after the post-processing.

4.1.2 Performance of ice classification

The classification performance of IceDetectNet was examined by quantifying the accuracy with which detected components are categorized into their respective basic habit and microphysical process classes (following the multi-label classification scheme detailed in Sect. 2). As discussed in Sect. 3.3, the basic habit of an ice crystal (i.e., image scale) is determined by the largest bounding box. The presence or absence of an aged classification is based on the detection of aging signatures among all bounding boxes, while aggrega-

Figure 3. (a) Histogram of the number of hand-labeled (orange) and model-predicted (brown) bounding boxes (average over five models). Instances with more than three bounding boxes are combined into a single category, whereas instances with no detected bounding boxes (11) are excluded. (b) Histogram of the number of predicted bounding boxes for hand-labeled aggregated (blue) and non-aggregated (orange) ice crystals. The shaded orange and blue regions denote areas of over-detection and under-detection, respectively. Panel (c) is the same as panel (b) but all bounding boxes larger than one are combined, thereby providing an intuitive visualization of the percentages of over-detection and under-detection.

tion is defined by ice crystals with more than one bounding box. We evaluated the performance of the five trained models using the cross-validation approach described in Sect. 3.8.1. The overall accuracies for the five models; their mean values; and the mean F1 scores for ice multi-label classification (19 classes), basic habit classification (7 classes), and microphysical process classification (4 classes) are shown in Table 3. The mean overall accuracies range between 78 % (for multi-label classification) and 86 % (for basic habit classification) and, thus, indicate good classification performance. Standard deviation values of the overall accuracy (OA) below 1 % on all data demonstrate robust results among the five models. In contrast, the performance on average F1 scores, ranging from 54.9 % (for multi-label classification) to 78.8 % (for basic habit classification) is generally worse than that on average OA values, indicating that IceDetectNet performs worse on rare classes. Furthermore, the low standard deviation values of averaged F1 scores (below 2 %) on all data further indicate that the five models have relatively similar results.

To gain further insights into IceDetectNet's performance in each ice category, we analyzed the confusion matrices (mean of five models) for basic habit classification (Fig. 4) and microphysical process classification (Fig. 5). IceDetectNet achieved an overall accuracy of 86 % for the basic habit categories (Fig. 4). The confusion matrix shows that IceDetectNet performed well for the ice categories that are represented as a large fraction in the dataset, like column (precision of 90 %, 1978 instances) and small (precision of 93 %, 324 instances). However, IceDetectNet encountered challenges with respect to accurately classifying rare classes such as plate (67 %, 47 instances) and lollipop (77 %, 73 instances). The main source of misclassification for plate ice crystals was confusion with the column class (7 instances). For the microphysical process category (Fig. 5), IceDetectNet achieved an overall accuracy of 82 %. While the model

performed well with respect to identifying pristine ice crystals (92 %), it showed worse performance for predicting aggregate (47 %) and aged–aggregate (49 %) ice crystals. This might be explained by the imbalanced dataset: pristine ice crystals dominated with a total contribution of 66 %. This suggests that balancing the dataset could further optimize IceDetectNet's classification performance for aggregate and aged–aggregate ice crystals in future iterations. A closer examination of the misclassified ice crystal images shows that the primary source of error was an under-detection of the number of bounding boxes. For example, in an image containing two aged columns, only one column–aged crystal was detected resulting in it being mislabeled as aged instead of aged–aggregate.

To investigate the classification performance of IceDetectNet in simpler scenarios, we evaluated the performance on non-aggregated ice and aggregated ice separately (Table 4). The evaluation on non-aggregated ice provides a benchmark, as non-aggregated ice images consist of a single ice component and, thus, allow us to compare the performance to traditional deep learning algorithms. When considering only non-aggregated ice crystals, IceDetectNet has an accuracy of 82 % for all data, 90 % for basic habits, and 85 % for microphysical processes (Table 3). Previous studies using single-label classification (Xiao et al., 2019; Jaffeux et al., 2022; Zhang, 2021) have reported overall accuracies above 90 %, which is higher compared with IceDetectNet for all data (82 %). However, for the multi-label classification, IceDetectNet classifies both basic habits and microphysical processes. While non-aggregated ice does not have an aggregation process, aging processes are still present. When one considers solely the basic habit classification, the accuracy of IceDetectNet (90 %) for non-aggregated ice closely aligns with the results reported in the aforementioned studies. Thus, under the same classification domain, IceDetectNet performs

Table 3. Overall accuracy of the multi-label, basic habit, and microphysical process ice classification. The table displays the overall accuracy values for each of the five models, along with the mean and standard deviation (SD) values (all reported as percentages). The validation set is broken down into aggregate (Agg) and non-aggregate (Non-agg) subsets. For the full validation set, the mean OA and F1 score are highlighted in bold.

		1	2	3	4	5	Mean OA	Mean F1 score	SD-OA	SD-F1
Multi-label	All data (19-class)	78.1	78.0	78.3	77.0	79.4	78.2	54.9	0.9	1.9
	Non-agg (10-class)	82.5	81.3	81.3	83.5	82.0	82.1	71.7	0.9	1.6
	Agg (9-class)	46.1	53.7	54.4	47.0	50.5	50.3	41.4	3.8	5.9
Basic habit	All data (7-class)	86.5	86.5	86.3	85.6	87.2	86.4	78.8	0.6	1.3
	Non-agg (7-class)	89.4	90.0	89.4	88.8	90.7	89.7	81.8	0.7	1.3
	Agg (6-class)	71.7	76.1	72.6	70.7	71.3	72.5	58.5	2.1	3.4
Microphysical processes	All data (4-class)	81.4	82.0	81.3	80.8	82.6	81.6	66.9	0.7	1.1
	Non-agg (2-class)	85.6	84.0	84.6	84.7	86.2	85.0	84.3	0.9	1.0
	Agg (2-class)	48.9	55.0	56.1	48.3	52.4	52.1	62.3	3.5	2.8

Figure 4. Confusion matrix of the mean performance of the basic habit classification for the training dataset (mean of five models). The y axis represents predicted values, whereas the x axis represents hand-labeled values. The bottom black row presents the number of hand-labeled ice crystals (white) and precision (blue) in each class. The bottom-right box shows the overall number of ice crystals (white) and the overall accuracy (blue). The rightmost black column presents the number of ice crystals predicted (white) and the recall (blue) in each class. The boxes in the middle (non-black boxes) evaluate the hand-labeled and predicted labels of the classification. For example, the second box in the first row means that 101.6 ice crystals are predicted as column but the actual labels of these 101.6 ice crystals are columns on capped columns (CPCs). The percentage in this box represents the ratio of the number of ice crystals in this box (i.e., 101.6) to the total number of hand-labeled CPCs (i.e., 785).

Figure 5. Similar confusion matrix to that in Fig. 4 but for physical processes.

competitively with existing classification models and offers additional information regarding microphysical processes.

When shifting our focus to aggregated ice, the inherent complexity of classifying the multiple components of an aggregate becomes evident due to a decreased classification accuracy (Table 3). The accuracy drops to 50 % for multi-label, 72 % for basic habit, and 52 % for microphysical processes. The reduction in performance between non-aggregate and aggregate ice subsets was more pronounced for the classification of microphysical processes (85 %–52 %), compared with the classification of the basic habit (90 %–72 %). This suggests that the reduced performance of IceDetectNet in the all-class classification can be attributed primarily to the challenges with respect to classifying microphysical processes.

Table 4. Overall accuracy of the multi-label, basic habit, and microphysical process ice classification. The table displays the overall accuracy values for each of the five models, along with the mean and standard deviation (SD) values (all reported as percentages). The generalization dataset is broken down into aggregate (Agg) and non-aggregate (Non-agg) subsets. For the full validation set, the mean OA and F1 score are highlighted in bold.

		1	2	3	4	5	Mean OA	Mean F1 score	SD-OA	SD-F1
Multi-label	All data (14-class)	67.5	66.7	67.2	67.5	68.3	67.5	48.5	0.6	1.6
	Non-agg (8-class)	72.8	73.3	71.2	74.5	73.2	73.0	58.3	1.2	2.0
	Agg (6-class)	46.3	50.0	53.1	47.7	51.2	49.7	45.4	2.7	1.4
Basic habit	All data (7-class)	81.6	79.9	79.6	80.7	81.3	80.6	68.7	0.8	0.6
	Non-agg (5-class)	86.4	85.9	85.4	84.8	86.7	85.9	70.3	0.7	0.8
	Agg (5-class)	64.7	69.1	65.3	69.6	71.7	68.1	61.0	2.9	1.7
Microphysical processes	All data (4-class)	72.8	72.3	72.5	72.9	73.4	72.77	64.8	0.4	0.3
	Non-agg (2-class)	78.5	78.0	77.4	78.1	77.3	77.8	74.6	0.5	0.8
	Agg (2-class)	45.2	51.1	50.9	46.6	48.4	48.4	67.9	2.6	0.6

4.2 Detection and classification performance on the aggregated component scale

In the previous sections, the detection and classification performance of IceDetectNet was evaluated at the image scale. In this section, our focus shifts from the image scale to the aggregate component scale, specifically to the bounding boxes of aggregate ice crystals. To evaluate the detection and classification performance at the aggregate component level, we followed a structured approach:

1. *Pairing of bounding boxes.* For each hand-labeled bounding box of an aggregate, we search for the predicted bounding box with the highest IoU.
2. *Detection performance.* The detection was considered correct if the IoU between the paired predicted and hand-labeled bounding box was larger than 0.5, otherwise the detection was considered incorrect.
3. *Classification performance.* The classification was considered correct if the label of the hand-labeled bounding box matched the label of the paired predicted bounding box, otherwise it was considered incorrect.

In contrast to the previous sections where the mean performance of all five models was examined, the performance was evaluated on a single model which was randomly selected (due to the robustness among the model runs). We categorized the bounding boxes into small, medium, and large using the areas of the predicted bounding boxes. The thresholds were set at the 33 % and 66 % percentiles of all bounding box areas, corresponding to below 32 331 px, from 32 331 to 71 275 px, and above 71 275 px, respectively. For a more intuitive understanding, these ranges correspond to squares with side lengths of below 180 px, from 180 to 267 px, and above 267 px, respectively.

When evaluating the detection and classification performance of IceDetectNet at the aggregate component scale

for the three bounding box size categories (small, medium, large; Fig. 6), we find good detection performance among all size categories, with accuracies ranging between 84 % (small bounding box) and 72 % (large bounding box). The detection performance decreases for larger bounding box sizes, which might be explained by an increased variability in appearance, texture, and scale for larger bounding boxes. The classification accuracies for correctly detected bounding boxes ranged between 66 % and 71 %, with medium-sized boxes achieving the highest classification accuracy of 71 %. This suggests that medium boxes may offer an ideal balance between detectability and feature richness. Thus, IceDetectNet shows good detection and classification performance for bounding box sizes down to 662 px and up to 294 903 px.

In general, the detection performance of IceDetectNet at the aggregate component scale is higher (72 %–84 %) than the classification performance (66 %–71 %). When combining the detection and classification performance (i.e., detection \times classification), similar overall performance to that reported in Table 3 for the aggregate subset (i.e., image scale) is obtained (50 %). For example, the accuracy for small bounding boxes was determined to be 54.6 %, derived from the product of 65 % classification accuracy and 84 % detection accuracy. The higher performance with respect to detection compared with classification suggests that the lower performance observed in the aggregate subset compared with the non-aggregate subset (as described in Sect. 4.1.2) is primarily due to misclassifications and not misdetections.

4.3 Generalization ability of IceDetectNet

4.3.1 Generalization ability on aggregate detection

The generalization ability of IceDetectNet was evaluated by applying it to an independent generalization dataset, which was not used to train the algorithm and was collected during a different season (detailed in Sect. 2). The same evaluation for

Figure 6. Sunburst diagrams to evaluate the detection (Det) and classification (Class) performance for (a) small, (b) medium, and (c) large bounding box sizes. Inner layers show detection results, while outer layers show classification results. The percentages indicate the proportion of bounding boxes in each category that were correctly or incorrectly detected and classified.

detection and classification at the image scale was performed as for the training dataset (Sect. 4.1.1).

The detection performance for aggregates of the generalization dataset shows an overall accuracy of 84 %, with an over-detection error of 26 % and an under-detection error of 8 % (Fig. 7a, b). This corresponds to a 14 % decrease in over-detection and a 6 % increase in under-detection compared with the training dataset. It is consistent across both the training (as described in Sect. 4.1.1) and generalization datasets that over-detection is a larger problem than under-detection. However, the different ice category distribution in the generalization dataset, specifically the increase in the aggregate class from 12 % in the training dataset to 37.7 % in the generalization dataset, is likely responsible for the shift in under-detection and over-detection between the training and generalization datasets. Thus, when the algorithm is applied to the generalization dataset (with a higher fraction of aggregate ice crystals), the problem of over-detection is reduced but still exists.

4.3.2 Generalization ability on ice classification

The classification accuracy on the generalization dataset showed overall accuracies ranging from 67 % (for the all data category) to 80 % (for the basic habits category) (see Fig. 7c and Table 4). Consistent with the performance on the training dataset, the values of OA are still higher than the averaged F1 scores, ranging from 48.5 % (for the all data category) to 68.7 % (for the basic habit category) (see Table 4). Compared with the training dataset, the classification performance decreased. The most significant decrease of 11 % was observed in the classification of all classes on OA, while the smallest decrease was observed in the classification of basic habits (6 %) on OA and the classification of microphysical processes (2.1 %) on the averaged F1 score. The observed decrease in performance between the training and generalization datasets is small, especially when considering a domain shift, a situation in which the data distribution differs between the training and generalization datasets

(Stacke et al., 2020). Specifically, the training and generalization datasets have different compositions of non-pristine ice crystals, with 71 % in the training set and 94 % in the test set. IceDetectNet’s ability to adapt to different data compositions and maintain relatively high accuracy indicates the ability of the algorithm to generalize to different dataset characteristics. Within the non-aggregate subset, IceDetectNet showed good classification performance for all classes (73 %), basic habits (86 %), and microphysical processes (78 %) on OA (as summarized in Table 4). Although the averaged F1 scores are still lower than OA, the percentage decrease in the averaged F1 scores is smaller than in OA. In the aggregate subset, performance levels were lower than in the non-aggregate subsets (50 %–68 % on OA; 45 %–68 % on averaged F1 scores). The observed reduction in the aggregate subset is mainly due to a domain shift, reflecting the difference in aggregate ice fraction between the training (12 %) and generalization (38 %) datasets. The generalization dataset, with a higher proportion of aggregated ice, presented more complexity and variability. Aggregates, with their multiple bounding boxes and variable structures, are inherently more difficult to classify than non-aggregates. This increased complexity in the test set likely contributed to the drop in performance, highlighting the challenges posed by domain shifts in the data. Consistently low standard deviation values (below 3 % on OA; below 2 % on averaged F1 scores) were observed across all models in all data subsets, indicating the stable and reproducible performance of IceDetectNet. These standard deviation values represent the variability in classification performance among different runs or configurations of the IceDetectNet model.

To gain further insights into IceDetectNet’s performance in each ice category, we analyzed the confusion matrices (mean of five models) for basic habit classification (Fig. 8) and microphysical process classification (Fig. 9) for the generalization dataset as well.

IceDetectNet achieved an overall accuracy of 81 % for the basic habit categories (Fig. 8) The confusion matrix shows that IceDetectNet still performed better for the ice

Figure 7. Panels (a) and (b) show the same as Fig. 3b and c but for the generalization dataset. Panel (c) shows the overall accuracy of IceDetectNet for the training dataset (blue) and the generalization dataset (gray) with respect to classifying basic habits, microphysical processes, and all classes.

categories that comprise a large fraction of the dataset, like small ice crystals (precision of 90 %). However, among these, column classification performance had a large performance drop (18 % decrease in precision compared with the training dataset), and its two main misprediction sources were irregular and plate ice crystals, which represent almost all of the mispredictions (29 %). This could be due to the data distribution shift from column to plate. Under the general decreasing trend among all categories, the irregular class surprisingly has a 10 % increase in precision. The main misprediction of the irregular class comes from column ice crystals in both the training dataset and generalization data, which could be the reason that IceDetectNet learned many column features in the training dataset and, thus, distributed higher weights to these column features. In contrast, the number of column ice crystals is much lower in the generalization dataset and, thus, leads to better performance with respect to the classification of irregular ice crystals. For the missing categories, like lollipop and CPC, that had no actual occurrences, IceDetectNet still predicted 113 ice crystals as lollipop and 50 as CPC, with most misclassifications being irregular ice crystals. This problem is likely due to the model's handling of sparse data and its tendency to fit irregular into these less common categories, as irregular was associated with the most complex features and, thus, any unrecognizable shape is classed as irregular.

For the microphysical process category (Fig. 9), IceDetectNet achieved an overall accuracy of 73 % (with a 9 % drop compared with the training dataset). The model still performed well with respect to identifying pristine ice crystals (82 %). In contrast, it shows better performance with respect to predicting aggregate (17 % higher than in the training dataset) and aged–aggregate (7 % higher than in the training dataset) ice crystals. This could be due to the changes in the data distribution, especially the changes in the aggregate fraction from 12 % in the training dataset to 37.7 % in the generalization dataset, which further emphasizes the importance of the balance of the dataset. After checking the main source of misprediction, we can see that underdetection still

		Confusion matrix								
Predicted	Column	1751.0 71.64%	0.2 0.87%	787.4 11.50%	242.4 13.77%	55.8 1.65%	2836 61.72%			
	CPC	17.0 0.70%		31.6 0.46%	2.2 0.12%	1.8 0.05%	52 0.00%			
	Droplet	7.0 0.29%	13.4 58.26%	29.6 0.43%	19.0 1.08%	1.8 0.05%	70 18.93%			
	Irregular	418.6 17.13%	4.8 20.87%	5627.2 82.16%	242.6 13.78%	227.2 6.71%	6520 86.30%			
	Lollipop	7.4 0.30%		84.2 1.23%	2.8 0.16%	18.6 0.55%	113 0.00%			
	Plate	229.6 9.39%	4.6 20.00%	147.4 2.15%	1237.4 70.31%	27.6 0.82%	1646 75.15%			
	Small	13.4 0.55%		142.0 2.07%	13.6 0.77%	3051.6 90.17%	3220 94.75%			
	Sum_predicted	2444 71.64%	0 0.00%	23 58.26%	6849 82.16%	0 0.00%	1760 70.31%	3384 90.17%		
							14460 80.77%			
		Actual	Column	CPC	Droplet	Irregular	Lollipop	Plate	Small	Sum_actual

Figure 8. Similar confusion matrix to that in Fig. 4 but for the generalization dataset. The CPC and lollipop classes are missing in the dataset; thus, they are represented using “0” in the corresponding columns.

plays an important role, for example, the main source of misprediction of aggregate ice crystals is pristine ice crystals, which is a typical misprediction problem.

5 Discussion

There are still opportunities to improve the generalization ability of IceDetectNet, particularly in the area of accurate detection and classification of aggregated ice crystals. In the case of imbalanced datasets, balancing strategies such as oversampling or undersampling techniques can be considered. Enriching the training dataset with a more comprehensive and diverse collection of ice crystal data would im-

Figure 9. Similar confusion matrix to that in Fig. 5 but for the generalization dataset.

prove the robustness and generalization capabilities of the algorithm. However, gathering more training data is a time-consuming process; therefore, reducing the time needed for manual labeling of bounding boxes is an important task for future research. New techniques, including contrastive learning (Le-Khac et al., 2020) and unsupervised learning algorithms, should be investigated to reduce the need for extensive manual labeling. Furthermore, the efficacy of fine-tuning as an approach to include new ice crystal classes holds considerable promise for IceDetectNet. Fine-tuning – the process of adapting a pretrained model (i.e., IceDetectNet) to a new, although still related, dataset – has been validated in a variety of fields as a means of achieving improved performance with comparatively smaller datasets (Tajbakhsh et al., 2016). This technique is consistent with the broader concept of transfer learning (Pan and Yang, 2009), which has seen widespread success in adapting models to new domains of application.

As the current dataset used for the training of IceDetectNet does not include some basic habits, such as needles and rosettes, we plan to adapt IceDetectNet to include these categories once additional datasets containing these habits are available.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we introduced IceDetectNet, a novel rotated object detection algorithm that is able to classify ice crystals not only at the image scale but also down to the aggregate component scale. The algorithm was used in combination with a multi-label classification scheme that assigns both a

basic habit and microphysical processes to each ice component. The algorithm was trained and tested on two independent holographic ice crystal datasets, which were collected during the NASCENT campaign in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard.

The performance of IceDetectNet was evaluated in terms of its detection and classification performance, at both the image and aggregate component scale. At the image scale, IceDetectNet showed good detection performance, correctly classifying 92 % of the ice crystals into the aggregate and non-aggregate classes. In terms of classification performance, it achieved an overall accuracy of 86 % for basic habits and 81 % for microphysical processes. Moreover, IceDetectNet achieved comparable classification accuracies to traditional deep learning algorithms on the non-aggregate subset, whereas the classification accuracies were lower for the aggregate subset. At the component scale, IceDetectNet showed good detection and classification performance across all bounding box sizes, indicating its ability to accurately classify components of aggregated ice crystals down to 662 px.

The generalization ability of IceDetectNet was examined on an independent generalization dataset that was collected during a different season. IceDetectNet showed good detection performance with an overall accuracy of 84 %. Although the classification accuracy decreased compared with the training dataset, the overall accuracy remained satisfactory for basic habit (81 %) and microphysical process (72 %) classification. The aggregate subset showed lower performance compared with the non-aggregate subset, possibly due to imbalances in the dataset. This highlights the potential to further optimize the generalization ability of IceDetectNet through dataset-balancing techniques, enlargement of the training dataset, or fine-tuning.

However, the ice categories used in this study are specific to the environmental and microphysical conditions present during the collection of the training data. In addition, the distinction between small and irregular ice categories combines both size and shape information, making the distinction difficult to classify. While these categories are appropriate for the current dataset, they may pose challenges when applying IceDetectNet to other datasets or comparing results with existing studies. However, adding or refining categories can be easily achieved through model fine-tuning.

IceDetectNet provides detailed shape information on the basic habit and microphysical processes of ice crystals down to the aggregate component scale; thus, it has the potential to improve the estimates of microphysical properties, such as the riming rate, aggregation rate, and ice water content. Due to the good generalization ability of IceDetectNet, we expect that it can also be applied to other cloud imaging probes in connection with fine-tuning. This will help to better understand the radiative properties of clouds and the microphysical processes leading to precipitation formation.

Appendix A: Hand-labeling platform

An essential component of training the rotated object detection algorithm is the hand-labeling of bounding boxes and ice crystals, which was done through the hand-labeling platform created by AngoAI (2022). The platform offers a graphical user interface to draw bounding boxes, adjust their size and rotation, and assign labels (Fig. A1).

Appendix B: Detailed criteria for ice crystal classification

The classification of ice crystals into their respective basic habits and microphysical processes is a challenging task that requires a set of rules to ensure consistency and accuracy across the dataset. Here, we describe the criteria used for the multi-label classification of ice crystals. We randomly select several images from each category as examples (see Fig. B1) and present the process of how we hand-label an ice crystal (see Fig. B2).

The classification process begins by using human judgment to determine whether the ice particle is an aggregate that contains more than one component. If an ice crystal is not aggregated, the classification process proceeds directly with the classification of the basic habit. For aggregated crystals, the process differs between the training and evaluation of IceDetectNet. In training, each component is manually located with a bounding box (i.e., smallest rectangle box) around the component, and these boxes are then classified. In

the multi-label classification, only the largest visually identified component of the aggregate is classified, without drawing a bounding box. The classified basic habit of this largest component will represent the basic habit of the whole aggregate ice crystal.

The next step is to classify the basic habits of the ice crystals/components. If the basic habit is not recognizable (as defined in Table 1), the size of the ice/component is assessed by eye. Small crystals are classified as small, whereas all others are classified as irregular-aged. If the basic habit is recognizable, we classify based on shape. Special shapes, like lollipop-aged for lollipop-like crystals or frozen droplets for those with droplet features, are classified first. Rectangular-shaped ice crystals (with four distinct edges) are classified as columns, whereas rectangular-shaped ice crystals with multiple branches at the end of the maximum dimension are labeled CPC-aged. Note that the CPC-aged categories also include needle bundles with missing plate sections. Hexagonal crystals (with six distinct edges) are classified based on their aspect ratio: a high aspect ratio indicates a column, whereas a low aspect ratio indicates a plate. Crystals/components that do not fit these categories are considered irregular-aged.

Once the basic habit is determined, the appearance of the edges of the ice/component determines whether the ice/component is aged or not. As mentioned earlier (see Sect. 2), irregular, CPC, and lollipop-aged are aged by default, whereas small ice crystals are pristine by definition. Therefore, we only need to decide if column, plate and frozen drops are aged or not. Usually, when an ice/component is aged, it has some tiny bumps on the edges.

Figure A1. Overview of the graphical user interface for hand-labeling on the hub.ango.ai (AngoAI, 2022). Users can draw and adjust bounding boxes around components of aggregated ice and assign labels.

Figure B1. A randomly selected sample of ice crystal images from each category based on the multi-label classification scheme.

Figure B2. The process of classifying ice crystals.

Code and data availability. The data (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288739>, Zhang et al., 2024b), code (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288779>, Zhang et al., 2024a), and models (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288804>, Zhang et al., 2024c) are available via the links provided in the references.

Author contributions. HZ and XL collaborated closely to design and develop the algorithm architecture; they also conducted all of the model runs. FR and JH actively participated in discussions and gave suggestions regarding the development of the algorithm. JP collected the training and test data with assistance from ROD and JH and conducted the single-label hand-labeling at the image scale. Both HZ and XL labeled the bounding boxes for the training and test data. Subsequently, HZ relabeled the training and test data based on the proposed multi-label classification scheme. The manuscript was written by HZ, with valuable input and discussions from FR, JH, ROD, and XL. The initial idea for the classification scheme was conceived through discussions between ROD and HZ.

Competing interests. The contact author has declared that none of the authors has any competing interests.

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